

UZBEK POETRY THE BRIGHTEST STAR OF THE SKY

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Annotation: This article tells about the life and unique creative flight of Erkin Vahidov, the beloved poet of our people, master of words, humorist, anthropologist, who skillfully arranged the experiences of the human soul like pearls.

Keywords: playwright, publicist, lyricism, philosophical poems, observation, storytelling, narration, anecdote, hangoma, humor.

There is another powerful tool for discovering man, his spiritual world, and that is the art of words, fiction. It is no coincidence that literature is described as anthropology, and poets and writers as engineers of the human spirit.

The beloved poet of our people, public figure, Hero of Uzbekistan Erkin Vahidov is known not only as a poet, but also as a playwright, publicist and literary critic. The great artist shone in the sky of modern Uzbek poetry and presented a bouquet of beautiful, fluent and easy-to-read poems to the hearts of poets. When we get acquainted with the poet's creative path, we witness that the theme of the Motherland, our native people, feelings of love, man and his dreams, secrets and hopes are glorified. Many poets and writers have repeatedly mentioned in their memoirs that Erkin Vahidov was a man who not only reached the peak of creativity, but also reached the peak of humanity. Erkin Vahidov left a deep mark not only as a poet who wrote poems and comedies, but also as a ghazal writer who revived the weight of a dream.

Whether he chooses the theme of love, his deep lyricism and philosophical poems that are widely observed, his humorous poems based on life stories and events, or his dramas, which are considered to be one of the facets of a powerful magician, the field of journalism, the book's profound thoughts as a literary critic. he had a place in the net of his heart. As Umarali Normatov, a literary critic, puts it: is a feature of the best epics and poems of the period. " Some of the works of the People's Poet of Uzbekistan, multifaceted artist Erkin Vahidov in this genre also deserve to be considered as an example of high artistic creativity, born of the heartache.

While Erkin Vahidov's earlier works were characterized by elegant lyricism, playful poems, and ghazals, by this time poems based on events, folk wisdom, and legends had emerged. For example, "Shyness", "Old bathroom, old pelvis", "Savagoch", "Shum bola", "Jumladan qaldan adamlar". In the poem "Old

bathroom, old pelvis" in our people in all events in social and political movements there was only silence. In this sense, the poet concludes the poem:

As long as we are lucky:

Old bathroom, old pelvis ...

In his works, the poet created a series of "Anecdotes of Matmusa" in the sense of attracting the reader to the ditch and reminding him of the fundamental shortcomings and shortcomings of our lives through laughter. Anecdotes are extremely important in terms of a day full of laughter, to awaken the reader's inner world and feelings. If you look at it this way, it's the anecdotes that make the reader laugh. But at the heart of every anecdote is the social achievements and shortcomings of the period, surrounded by humor. The poet himself said of the anecdotes: "Everyone laughs when Donish reads the village anecdotes. Although I wrote them with pain," says the poet. These images are reflected in the image of the modern Efendi - Matmusa. Matmusa's anecdotes can be divided into two categories. The first category includes "Matmusa's Song", "Matmusa's Plate", "Matmusa's Tandoori" These include "Matmusa the Artist," "Matmusa's Dutori," "Matmusa in the Tandoor," "Matmusa's American Discovery," "Matmusa's Statue."

Especially among them, which are educationally thought-provoking, This is the nature of the anecdote "Matmusa dressed in a tandoor" in order to understand his mistakes and shortcomings and draw a fair conclusion. In Latifada, he is confused about how to take home the tandoor he bought at the market. He seems to have solved the problem on his own, first riding on a donkey and putting on an oven. It is impossible to see the destination, only to look up at the sky, and the donkey goes in the opposite direction instead of going home. It is natural for Matmusa not to ask people where my house is. There are many of us who are in this situation of Matmusa. Finding a solution to a problem, and then finding a rational solution to it, requires an understanding approach to work. There are many people in every corner of life who have not found a solution to their problems. The strong and logical role of the anecdote ends, and the reader is asked what conclusions to draw.

Dear friends, lost,

Let's not laugh at a believer.

Like Matmus

Let's not wear a tandoor.

In Erkin Vahidov's series "Anecdotes of the Village" we laugh at Matmusa's noble deeds, but the bitter truth blows in their hearts. The most important thing

is to draw the right conclusions from each work and to be able to apply it to oneself.

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